

QUALITY IN PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT SIGNIFICANCE OF INDICATORS.

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Abstract: In the management of product quality, the unified state system of product quality management provides information about the consumption and technical level of the product, increases the quality of the manufactured product, evaluates the product quality level, develops and supplies new types of products, prepares product production technology, material, and technical support, undertakes metrological supply, personnel selection, and training, ensuring constant uniformity, transportation, storage, supply, field inspection, quality promotion, and quality indicators.

Keywords: quality, product, planning, mechanism, conformity, certificate, resource, standard, the international standard, normative document, technical documents, facility, system.

Product quality management is the role of quality indicators during product creation, operation, or consumption. Quality management means ensuring an acceptable level at the design and construction stage, adapting it to modern scientific and technical capabilities and customer requirements, and then providing these quality indicators in a real product during the production process. This level can be achieved by developing and implementing comprehensive product quality management systems at the international level. The state standardization system serves as the main factor of product quality management [1].

The standards for the complex quality management system consist of

international standards that define the goal, i.e. international standards of requirements for product quality, standards that ensure the achievement of the goal, that is, regulation of factors affecting quality. Must be involved in all phases of sales assortment and quality control. During the design and research phase, sales organizations must place orders with manufacturing and design enterprises to create or update new types of products. When accepting an experimental sample, the sales staff gives one of the decisive votes, because they must correctly assess the consumer properties of the new product. At the stage of handling and distribution, sales staff should create the conditions of storage, transportation, and sale of goods in such a way that they should not be damaged as a product. At this stage, products should be accepted according to quality indicators [2]. At the stage of operation and consumption, it is necessary to organize the processes of proper operation of goods, their service, restoration of quality, and disposal of outdated products. Sales should communicate this information to customers. In our country, there is a single-state system of product quality management. Its main goal is to produce high-quality products at a low cost. Such a goal can be realized only by the wide and consistent introduction of science and technology achievements and advanced experience into production. The above system is based on the production of products based on the state standard [3].

The unified state system of product quality management is designed to develop and master a wide range of new products. The unified state system of product quality management provides information on product consumption and technical level, increases the quality of manufactured products, evaluates the product quality level, develops and supplies new products, prepares product production technology, material and technical support, metrological support, personnel selection. and undertakes preparation, constant uniformity, transportation, storage, supply, field inspection, quality promotion [4].

In general, the scientific and technical level of the normative document should be compared to the details of the quality **indicators**. Task and technical efficiency

indicators, productivity, accuracy of gassing, food products, **construction indicators, overall dimensions**, assembly coefficient, interchangeability coefficient, **composition and structure indicators**, percentage of alloying additives in steel, the concentration of various impurities in acids, amount of synthetic fibers in gassing, amount of food products and useful substances.

Accuracy indicators. Durability describes the ability of an object to continuously maintain its operability for a certain period or during a certain amount of work. **Failure performance** metrics include failure probability, failure rate, average work done before failure, and gamma-percent work done before failure [5]. **Endurance describes the ability** of an object to maintain its operational capability under a defined maintenance and repair system until it reaches an extreme state. Multi-resilience indicators include average work resources, specified work resources, gamma-percentage resources, and resources. **Repairability describes the ability** of an object to prevent failure and identify the causes of failure and eliminate the consequences of failure through repair and maintenance. Repairability indicators include the probability of recovery and the average time spent on recovery. **The** indicators of recovery include the average time of recovery to the specified value of the quality indicator and the degree of recovery [6]. **Shelf** life describes the state of integrity and serviceability of an object or the condition of a product for consumption during and after storage and after transportation. Shelf life indicators include average shelf life and gamma percent shelf life. **Resource-saving indicators describe the characteristics of the product** that reflect its technical excellence in terms of the level of demand for raw materials, materials, fuel, energy, and labor resources [7]. Indicators of saving resources consist of three subgroups of indicators of economical use of raw materials and materials, including comparative consumption of raw materials, comparative consumption of materials, destruction of raw materials under specified conditions, and destruction of materials under specified conditions. **Indicators of energy consumption efficiency**, including specific fuel consumption, specific energy consumption, useful work coefficient, etc. are included. As

indicators of efficient use of energy, comparative indicators are usually used, that is, the ratio of consumed energy and fuel to the volume of produced products or useful work performed. As generalized indicators describing the economical use of raw materials, materials, fuel, energy, and labor resources, indicators describing the costs of product development, preparation, and use can be used [8].

Ergonomic indicators describe the "man-object" system and take into account the set of hygienic, anthropometric, physiological, and psychological characteristics that occur in human life. Ergonomic indicators include noise level, light level, temperature level, compatibility of product construction with human speed capabilities, and compliance of product construction with human power capabilities [9].

Aesthetic indicators are characterized by the meaning of information, the acceptability of the form, the completeness of the structure and the perfect preparation, the original copy, stylistic compatibility, fashion compatibility, functional-structural adaptation, the orderliness of the volume-spatial structure, harmony of colors, careful coating and decoration of the surface, company signs. consists of:

Technological - describes the properties of the composition and structure or construction of the product that can ensure the lowest costs in production, use, and restoration of quality indicators, production, and work performance conditions. It takes into account the relative labor cost of product preparation, the relative cost of material, the relative cost of energy, and the one-time average labor cost of this type of technical service [10].

Adaptability for transportation describes the suitability of the product for moving in an open place, that is, for activities that are not related to the use of the product. Indicators of adaptability for transportation include the average time of preparing the product for transportation, the average labor cost when preparing the product for transportation, the average time spent when loading the product onto a

certain type of vehicle, and unloading the product from a certain type of vehicle. including average time consumption, and vehicle capacity utilization factors.

Standardization and homogenization indicators represent the enrichment of the product with standard, standardized, and original components, as well as the level of integration with other products. Standardization and homogenization indicators include applicability, reproducibility, and homogenization coefficients.

Patent-legal indicators describe the level of innovation of technology solutions used in the product, their patent protection, as well as the possibility of unhindered purchase in the country and abroad. Patent-legal indicators include patent protection indicators, and patent purity indicators [11].

Ecological indicators describe the level of harmful effects on the environment that occur when using or consuming a product. When choosing and determining these indicators, environmental protection requirements are taken into account. Environmental indicators include the permitted amount of harmful compounds released into the environment, and the probability of releasing harmful particles, gases, and radiation into the environment during product storage, transportation, use, or consumption.

Safety indicators describe the properties and characteristics of the product's safety in use for human life, health and property, and for the environment. Safety indicators are formed by product types based on the guidance document on the formation of product indicators in regulatory documents, for example, the safety indicators of electrical equipment and products include the class of protection against the electric current, labor safety during management, service, operation, the presence of a device for constant insulation testing, noise level, nitrogen oxides, the relative amounts of which are released into the environment. Acidity, microbiological indicators, pesticides, and heavy metals for milk and milk products [12].

Checking the quality of products refers to the conformity of quality and morphological indicators of products with regulatory and technical documents.

From the production of products to the recipient, they are checked several times. There are operational, acceptance, and revenue checks. **Operational** – checked after each step. **Acceptance inspection** - performed at the end of production. The stamp of the quality control department indicates that the product is of good quality. **Income inspection** is the process of receiving raw materials and products for sale according to their quality. There are two types of product quality control: comprehensive and selective [13]. More selective verification is used because this method takes less time. Electric lamps shall be tested for 10 seconds each at a voltage 15% higher than the rated voltage. Then the burn in 15-200 W lamps should not exceed 1.5%, then they are acceptable. Otherwise, the document will be drawn up and sent back to production. Due to a large number of quality and morphological indicators of products, it is difficult to analyze them all. For this reason, various tests are shown depending on the program of checking standards in the "Rules of Admission" section. Acceptance tests are where the sample is thoroughly checked before the product is put into production. At the end of the production process, inspection of the finished product by the technical control department for some indicators by the requirements of the regulatory document. The results are marked in the documents that are sent along with the goods. Industrial enterprises are subject to periodic inspections to ensure quality stability. One-size-fits-all tests. In this case, tests are conducted every 2-3 years to test the strength [14]. It is tested once every 5 years to determine its suitability for repair. Products are divided into qualitative groups according to 3 characters (quality, quantity, alternative). The product is divided into varieties according to the quality mark and accepted. Window glasses are divided into high class 1 and 2 types, and model shoes are divided into 2 types. Depending on the manifestation of defects, they are divided into obvious and hidden types. Defects are divided into serious, major, and non-serious types according to their size. Defects are divided into the material, construction, technology, and finishing defects by origin. Acceptance of products according to the quantity mark. In this, the quality indicators of the product will be determined and compared with

the requirements of regulatory and technical documents. Inspection of products by the alternative mark is widely used in trade, products are divided into usable and unusable types depending on whether they meet the requirements of the standard [15].

Classification of industrial products in the conditions of the market economy, scientific-methodical support for product quality assessment, and relations between the producer and the consumer should almost correspond to the characteristics of goods and money. For this, it is necessary to solve these complex issues, including separating the characteristics and indicators that describe the quality of the product from each side, expressing the product and its quality in regulatory documents, taking into account the interconnected quality, quantity, and prices of the consumer to objectively assess the quality of joint products in stages, to obtain all the necessary objective and practical information about product quality and its technical level and competitiveness at each stage of the "quality ring".

Basing the selection of the nomenclature of product quality indicators is carried out based on the conditions of use and function of the product, the analysis of consumer requirements, the composition and structure describing product quality, and the main requirements for quality indicators.

Factors affecting product quality are technical, organizational, economic, and social. **Technical factors** include the condition of equipment, tools, and controls, technical documents, raw materials, quality of semi-finished products, and the like. **Organizational factors** include planning, teamwork, technical service, equipment repair; materials, components, and equipment, provision of tools with technical documents and control tools, production culture, organization of work on a scientific basis, meals, organization of rest during work, etc. Forms of payment of wages to **economic factors, amount of monthly salary**; financial incentives for high-quality products and work, deductions from monthly salary for product defects, quality level, cost, product price, and the like. **Social factors** include selection and placement of personnel, organization of training, organization of scientific and

technical creativity, creativity and inventiveness, living conditions, mutual relations, the psychological climate in the team, and educational work.

The establishment of product quality is manifested in research and design, production, circulation, consumption, or use at all stages of its life. Research and design work play a decisive role in increasing the quality of the product. This stage is considered the beginning of the establishment of quality, which is achieved as a result of the application of scientific and technical progress and as a result of the preparation of regulatory documents for the production of products in compliance with the economic indicators set for their circulation, consumption or use. At this stage, activities include conducting scientific research, experimental design, and other work focused on templates, samples with quality indicators, developing and introducing regulatory documents, self-monitoring of compliance with standards, perspective and standardization of product quality, product to achieve the planned level of quality, to introduce measures of preparation of various methods, to develop the design and technological activities aimed at testing and control, to analyze information about the quality of similar products produced in our country and abroad, to classify and determine indicators of product quality, as well as to assess the level of quality. Product quality management systems ensure that the development of the technical level at the development stage is always at a high pace. For complex and responsible products, special work plans are drawn up during the development quality management process. It is possible to develop new product samples in special design research or design institutes, industrial enterprises, and design technological departments (bureaus). In this case, the main attention is focused on whether the sample of this product is new or improved products in its production. It is a difficult and responsible task to choose the optimal technological processes at the stage of preparing the product for production because at this stage it will be difficult to constantly improve the technology and improve the economic indicators of production. Improving product quality at the stage of preparation is one of the main tasks of the enterprise.

At the stage of product production, the preparation of the product is carried out directly, ensuring and controlling the quality of equipment, equipment, control and measuring equipment at the required level, improving the quality of the product, preventing unfitness, preparing and implementing measures to eliminate the causes of non-compliant product production, regulatory introduction of documents and strict compliance with them, establishment of incoming control of raw materials, materials, semi-finished products and completed products entering the enterprise, establishment of control of production, acceptance and testing of released products, compliance with inspection control, regulatory documents, information about the quality of products at the stage of use collecting and collecting, taking into account and analyzing its unusability, complaints about it, raw materials, materials, semi-finished products, components and finished products in warehouses, transports within the enterprise, according to regulatory documents It is planned to carry out measures to ensure and control the production of products of the specified quality level, to provide material and moral encouragement to the employees of the enterprise.

Product quality management systems ensure the achievement of goals and tasks set at the production stage in production associations and enterprises. The direction of management at the stages of trade and sales is aimed at creating the necessary conditions for product storage, transport, and sales following planned tasks, standards, and technical conditions. When transporting the product in vehicles, it is expected to observe the rules of loading and unloading. When storing the finished product in warehouses, it is necessary to protect it from heat and other adverse effects. At this stage, the quality of the finished product must be maintained at a high level, and quality management systems ensure that it is delivered to the consumer under the specified quality indicators. To achieve these goals, the enterprise prepares to collect, process and analyze information about the use and storage of consumer products and their compliance with consumer needs, provide consumers with the necessary documents for use and repair, carry out warranty

repairs of products, provide consumers with spare parts, tools, and manufactured goods. It is important to take measures to provide items.

Factors affecting product quality can be identified and eliminated through quality systems, which are activities that include quality in all aspects, ensure all aspects of it, and cover all life stages of the product. Currently, such systems can be created with the development, implementation, and certification of the quality management system in enterprises following the requirements of international standards of the ISO 9000 series.

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